

METHODICAL ORGANIZATION OF A TRAINING SESSION ON THE STUDY OF WORKS OF RUSSIAN FANTASY USING TECHNOLOGY FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF CRITICAL THINKING

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Abstract. *the purpose of this article is to introduce students to the main works of Russian fiction literature and teach them to analyze in depth by developing critical thinking skills. Training is organized using critical thinking development technologies, including problem Education, a dialogue-based approach, and problem-situation resolution techniques. In the process of studying Russian fiction, students are given a wider understanding of the specific styles, genre features, and the social and cultural significance of the genre of fiction. In this, activities are carried out aimed at analyzing literary works, studying characters and events on the basis of a critical approach, contextual analysis of the text and determining the philosophical and aesthetic views of writers. The emphasis is on interactive techniques, group discussions, and individual thought expression. With the help of critical thinking technology, students not only learn literary criticism through Russian fantastic works, but also develop skills to apply an analytical and creative approach to solving life problems. This methodology is aimed at expanding the worldview of students, teaching them to express their thoughts in a grounded and analytical way.*

Keywords: *Russian fiction, the development of critical thinking, a literary work.*

МЕТОДИЧЕСКАЯ ОРГАНИЗАЦИЯ ОБУЧАЮЩЕГО ЗАНЯТИЯ ПО ИЗУЧЕНИЮ ПРОИЗВЕДЕНИЙ РУССКОГО ФАНТАСТИЧЕСКОГО ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ РАЗВИТИЯ КРИТИЧЕСКОГО МЫШЛЕНИЯ

Аннотация. *цель данной статьи-познакомить учащихся с основными произведениями русской фантастики и научить их более глубоко анализировать их посредством развития навыков критического мышления. Занятия организуются с использованием технологий развития критического мышления, включая проблемное обучение, коммуникативный подход и методы решения проблемных ситуаций. В процессе изучения произведений русской художественной литературы учащимся дается более широкое представление о специфике стилей, жанровых особенностях крупных писателей, а также о социальном и культурном значении жанра художественной литературы. При этом осуществляется анализ литературных произведений, изучение персонажей и событий на основе критического подхода, контекстный анализ текста и деятельность, направленная на определение философских и эстетических взглядов писателей. На*

занятиях упор делается на интерактивные методы, групповые обсуждения и выражение индивидуальных мнений. С помощью технологии критического мышления учащиеся не только изучают литературоведение через произведения русской фантастики, но и развивают навыки применения аналитического и творческого подхода к решению жизненных задач. Данная методика направлена на расширение кругозора учащихся, обучение их аргументированному и аналитическому выражению своих мыслей.

Ключевые слова: Русская фантастика, развитие критического мышления, литературное произведение.

Introduction

Critical thinking is a complex and multifaceted activity of a person that occurs in the process of mastering knowledge. It is important not only in the process of teaching, but also in society and in everyday life. Critical thinking development techniques for teachers and education system staff help to master reading, writing and analysis skills more deeply and broadly. Especially in the study of fiction, the importance of critical thinking technology increases further, as there are many complex, personal and metaphorical concepts in the fantasy genre.

This article will consider the main methods and techniques of the technology for the development of critical thinking in the teaching of works of Russian fantasy. The literature of Russian fantasy has created a unique and colorful world, and in this world it gives students the opportunity to receive education beyond their peers or lessons. Critical thinking is necessary in order to analyze the works in depth, understand the opinion of the author of the work and create his own opinion.

Definition and importance of critical thinking

Critical thinking is the process of analyzing and evaluating one's own knowledge and experience. One of the main aspects of critical thinking is that it frequently motivates a person to make their own decisions with suspicion and caution. This is an ability that is necessary not only in academia, but also in everyday life. In the context of reading and literary analysis, critical thinking assumes the study of works not only in terms of content, but also in terms of the author's hidden intentions, how he illuminates themes and ideas, and how he shapes personal thoughts.

The technology for the development of critical thinking includes various methods and techniques for teachers. These techniques make it possible to establish an interactive dialogue with students, to analyze the idea in depth, as well as to express their point of view in a free and justified way. The role of critical thinking in the educational process is extremely large, since it helps students not only to receive information, but also to critically analyze and assimilate it.

Russian fantasy literature: a general image

Russian fantasy literature is characterized by its rich heritage and fantastic images. Works written in this genre reflect not only imagination, but also the deepest views of mankind, experience and knowledge. The fantasy genre developed in Russian literature in the late 19th and early 20th centuries, and continues to be popular today.

First of all, it is necessary to talk about the outstanding works of Russian fantasy. One of them is the Viy story of Nikolai Gogol, which depicts elements of folklore and ancient beliefs of the Russian people. Also, the works of Alexei Tolstoy and Mikhail Bulgakov are characteristic examples of Russian fantasy. These works are not only fantastic stories, but also take deep social and philosophical issues into them.

Technologies for the development of critical thinking

There are a number of technologies for the development of critical thinking. The use of these in the teaching process helps students to understand the work more deeply and increases their ability to express their thoughts. The following methods and techniques are used to effectively apply critical thinking technologies:

1. Dialogical method-to involve students in the discussion process. In this method, new perspectives on the work can be discovered by exchanging ideas between readers.
2. Problem method-the development of critical thinking in students through problem situations. When studying fantasy works, it is important to encourage readers to ask questions about the author's views and worldview.
3. The projective method is to allow students to create their own personal thoughts. In this method, the student can write a unique fantasy work or modify an existing work to create new perspectives.
4. Methods of analysis and synthesis – encourage readers to deeply analyze the content of the work and form their own thoughts based on this analysis. Through this method, readers will help to understand the main idea of the work and interpret it based on their own thoughts.

Creative approaches are the development of the creative potential of students and the formation of the ability to think critically in them. For example, comparing the thematic issues indicated by the author of the work with his own worldview.

Methods of studying the works of Russian fantasy in the development of critical thinking

In order to effectively organize training sessions, a number of methods and techniques can be used in the analysis of works of Russian fantasy. Below are some styles:

1. Layer-by – layer analysis of a work-fantasy works are often multi-layered. Involving readers in the study of the work on several floors, for example, first analyzing the plot, then the character of the characters, and finally the philosophical and spiritual issues in the work.
2. Taking into account the social and cultural context – when reading works of Russian fantasy, it is important to analyze their written period, social and political circumstances. This helps readers understand what social issues the author has focused on.
3. Metaphorical analysis-in the works of Russian fantasy there are many metaphors, symbols and allegories. To encourage readers to analyze these metaphors and to help them understand the Deep Meanings of the works.
4. Connecting with personal experience is to allow students to compare their experiences and worldviews with works, through which they further develop their critical thinking.

The role of critical thinking in the study of the works of Russian fantasy

The main goal in the study of Russian fantasy is to develop imagination, logical analysis and creativity in students. Reading a fantasy is not just an idea, but an awareness of the deep ideas and motives behind it. Critical thinking, at the same time, helps readers understand the historical, cultural and philosophical layers in Russian fantasy. This allows students not only to read literature, but also to see the world in general critically.

Conclusion

The technology for the development of critical thinking is of great importance in the study of the works of Russian fantasy. Through the use of these technologies in their lessons, teachers teach students not only to read literature, but also to form personal thoughts, to deeply analyze the work. Russian fantasy, on the other hand, serves as an excellent resource for students to form a broad worldview and freely express their thoughts.

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